

Distance functions of carabids in crop fields depend on functional traits, crop type and adjacent habitat: a synthesis

ESM 3: Post-processing and visualization of marginal predictions

Fabian A. Boetzl Douglas B. Sponsler Matthias Albrecht Péter Batáry
Klaus Birkhofer Michal Knapp Jochen Krauss Bea Maas
Emily A. Martin Clélia Sirami Louis Sutter Colette Bertrand
Aliette Bosem Baillod Gerard Bota Vincent Bretagnolle Lluís Brotons
Thomas Frank Moritz Fusser David Giralt Ezequiel González
Anouschka Hof Henryk Luka Ronan Marrec Michael A. Nash
Katherina Ng Manuel Plantegenest Brigitte Poulin Gavin Siriwardena
Teja Tschardtke Matthias Tschumi Aude Vialatte Laura Van Vooren
Muhammad Zubair-Anjum Martin H. Entling Ingolf Steffan-Dewenter
Jens Schirmel

2023-11-27

Contents

Summary	2
Prepare environment	3
Load packages	3
Load data and models	3
Define custom functions	4
Plotting functions	4
epred extraction	4
Generate marginal predictions	5
Get epred	5
Collate for convenient handling, and clear memory to avoid crashes	5
Extract distance ranges to constrain plots	7
Get average marginal and conditional effects	7
Set up rugs for plotting	8
Visualize	9
By crop	9
By habitat	12
Grand mean	15
References	17

Summary

This appendix details model post-processing and the visualization of marginal predictions. There are several valid ways of calculating marginal model predictions, and the choice of which to use depends on the intended interpretation.

First, there is the question of what *kind* of prediction we're making. The `tidybayes` package (Kay 2020) has helper functions for generating four kinds of predictions. From https://mjskay.github.io/tidybayes/reference/add_predicted_draws.html:

`add_epred_draws()` adds draws from expectation of the posterior predictive distribution to the data. It corresponds to `rstanarm::posterior_epred()` or `brms::posterior_epred()`.

`add_predicted_draws()` adds draws from posterior predictive distribution to the data. It corresponds to `rstanarm::posterior_predict()` or `brms::posterior_predict()`.

`add_linpred_draws()` adds draws from (possibly transformed) posterior linear predictors (or “link-level” predictors) to the data. It corresponds to `rstanarm::posterior_linpred()` or `brms::posterior_linpred()`.

`add_residual_draws()` adds draws from residuals to the data. It corresponds to `brms::residuals.brmsfit()`

We will use `tidybayes::add_epred_draws()`, which uses the posterior to predict mean values of the response variable. This corresponds to the default behavior of the `brms::conditional_effects()` (Bürkner 2017).

Then there is the question of what to do with the varying effect of study/site. This is controlled by the `re_formula` argument in `tidybayes::add_epred_draws()`. One option is to make predictions imagining a random draw of one study/site combination (`re_formula = NULL`), thereby incorporating all the uncertainty of the study/site effect (thus creating wider intervals). Another option is to ignore the varying effects (`re_formula = NA`), which amounts to imagining a hypothetical study/site combination that is the average of all observed study/site combinations (that is, the global effect from which the varying effects deviate). We will go with the latter option, which again corresponds to the default behavior of `brms::conditional_effects()` (Bürkner 2017).

For further reading:

<https://www.andrewheiss.com/blog/2021/11/10/ame-bayes-re-guide/#posterior-predictions>

<https://github.com/paul-buerkner/brms/issues/82#issuecomment-231440994>

Prepare environment

Load packages

```
library(tidybayes)
library(ggdist)
library(patchwork)
library(tidyverse)
```

Load data and models

```
##### Data files #####
meta_rich <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich.rds")
meta_rich_predatory <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_predatory2.rds")
meta_rich_granivorous <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_granivorous.rds")
meta_rich_omnivorous <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_omnivorous2.rds")
meta_rich_omnivorous_b <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_omnivorous3.rds")
meta_abund <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund.rds")
meta_abund_diet <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund_diet2.rds")
meta_abund_diet_b <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund_diet3.rds")
meta_abund_size <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund_size.rds")

##### Richness models #####
## Aggregate
brm_rich_00 <- readRDS("../output/brm_rich_00.rds")

## Predatory
brm_rich_11 <- readRDS("../output/brm_rich_11.rds")

## Omnivorous
brm_rich_12 <- readRDS("../output/brm_rich_12.rds")

## Omnivorous (without Poecilus cupreus)
brm_rich_12b <- readRDS("../output/brm_rich_12b.rds")

## Granivorous
brm_rich_20 <- readRDS("../output/brm_rich_20.rds")

##### Activity density models #####
## Aggregate
brm_abund_00 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_00.rds")

## Predatory
brm_abund_11 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_11.rds")

## Omnivorous
brm_abund_12 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_12.rds")

## Omnivorous (without Poecilus cupreus)
brm_abund_12b <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_12b.rds")

## Granivorous
brm_abund_20 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_20.rds")

## Small
brm_abund_30 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_30.rds")

## Medium
brm_abund_40 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_40.rds")

## Large
brm_abund_50 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_50.rds")
```

Define custom functions

Plotting functions

```
# prep data for rug plots
get_rug <- function(x, name) {

  x %>%
  select(crop.pool, snh.type, distance100) %>%
  distinct() %>%
  filter(distance100 <= 0.65) %>%
  mutate(model = name)

}
```

epred extraction

```
# ~ distance
get_epred <- function(x, name) {

  x %>%
  add_epred_draws(
    # predict out to 100 meters
    newdata = expand_grid(distance100 = seq(0, 0.65, by = 0.01),
                          # condition on mean(log.trap.days)
                          log.trap.days = mean(meta_rich$log.trap.days),
                          study = NA, # ignore study
                          site = NA, # ignore site
                          # include all SNH
                          snh.type = c("control", "herbaceous", "woody"),
                          # include all crops
                          crop.pool = c("Cereal", "Legume", "Maize",
                                         "Oilseed", "Vegetable")),

    re_formula = NA, # ignore group level (i.e. "random") effects
    allow_new_levels = TRUE) %>%
  mutate(distance = distance100 * 100, # rescale distance back to meters
         model = name) # plotting convenience

}

# ~ trap.days
get_epred2 <- function(x, name) {

  x %>%
  add_epred_draws(
    newdata = expand_grid(distance100 = 0.25, # fix distance at 25 m
                          log.trap.days = seq(
                            min(meta_rich$log.trap.days),
                            max(meta_rich$log.trap.days) + 0.05, by = 0.1
                          ),
                          # the + 0.05 is so that we cover the full range given the 0.1 step size
                          study = NA, # ignore study
                          site = NA, # ignore site
                          snh.type = c("control", "herbaceous", "woody"), # include all SNH
                          crop.pool = c("Cereal", "Legume", "Maize",
                                         "Oilseed", "Vegetable")), # include all crops

    re_formula = NA, # ignore group level (i.e. "random") effects
    allow_new_levels = TRUE) %>% # I think this needs to be TRUE?
  mutate(distance = distance100 * 100, # rescale distance back to meters
         model = name)

}
```

Generate marginal predictions

Get epred

Conditioned on all combinations of crop and snh.type and, for richness models, on mean(log.trap.days).

```
# Richness

brm_rich_00_epred <- get_epred(brm_rich_00, "01_brm_rich_00")
brm_rich_11_epred <- get_epred(brm_rich_11, "02_brm_rich_11")
brm_rich_12_epred <- get_epred(brm_rich_12, "03_brm_rich_12")
brm_rich_12b_epred <- get_epred(brm_rich_12b, "04_brm_rich_12b")
brm_rich_20_epred <- get_epred(brm_rich_20, "05_brm_rich_20")

brm_rich_00_epred_trap.days <- get_epred2(brm_rich_00, "01_brm_rich_00")
brm_rich_11_epred_trap.days <- get_epred2(brm_rich_11, "02_brm_rich_11")
brm_rich_12_epred_trap.days <- get_epred2(brm_rich_12, "03_brm_rich_12")
brm_rich_12b_epred_trap.days <- get_epred2(brm_rich_12b, "04_brm_rich_12b")
brm_rich_20_epred_trap.days <- get_epred2(brm_rich_20, "05_brm_rich_20")

# Activity density

brm_abund_00_epred <- get_epred(brm_abund_00, "06_brm_abund_00")
brm_abund_11_epred <- get_epred(brm_abund_11, "07_brm_abund_11")
brm_abund_12_epred <- get_epred(brm_abund_12, "08_brm_abund_12")
brm_abund_12b_epred <- get_epred(brm_abund_12b, "09_brm_abund_12b")
brm_abund_20_epred <- get_epred(brm_abund_20, "10_brm_abund_20")
brm_abund_30_epred <- get_epred(brm_abund_30, "11_brm_abund_30")
brm_abund_40_epred <- get_epred(brm_abund_40, "12_brm_abund_40")
brm_abund_50_epred <- get_epred(brm_abund_50, "13_brm_abund_50")
```

Collate for convenient handling, and clear memory to avoid crashes

```
# Remove model objects

rm(brm_rich_00, brm_rich_11, brm_rich_12, brm_rich_12b,
   brm_rich_20, brm_abund_00, brm_abund_11, brm_abund_12,
   brm_abund_12b, brm_abund_20, brm_abund_30, brm_abund_40,
   brm_abund_50)

gc()

##          used (Mb) gc trigger (Mb) max used (Mb)
## Ncells  3376548 180.4 11471381 612.7 11471381 612.7
## Vcells 1185749141 9046.6 2107249941 16077.1 2039973902 15563.8

# Pool richness models
```

```

epred_rich <- bind_rows(brm_rich_00_epred,
                        brm_rich_11_epred,
                        brm_rich_12_epred,
                        brm_rich_12b_epred,
                        brm_rich_20_epred) %>%
mutate(model = factor(
  model, levels = c("01_brm_rich_00", "02_brm_rich_11", "03_brm_rich_12",
                    "04_brm_rich_12b", "05_brm_rich_20")
)) %>%
mutate(crop.pool = tolower(crop.pool))

rm(brm_rich_00_epred, brm_rich_11_epred, brm_rich_12_epred, brm_rich_12b_epred,
   brm_rich_20_epred)

gc()

```

```

##          used (Mb) gc trigger (Mb) max used (Mb)
## Ncells  3374163 180.2 11471381 612.7 11471381 612.7
## Vcells 1167907005 8910.5 2107249941 16077.1 2107241324 16077.0

```

Pool trap.days epred

```

epred_rich.trapdays <- bind_rows(brm_rich_00_epred_trap.days,
                                  brm_rich_11_epred_trap.days,
                                  brm_rich_12_epred_trap.days,
                                  brm_rich_12b_epred_trap.days,
                                  brm_rich_20_epred_trap.days) %>%
mutate(model = factor(
  model, levels = c("01_brm_rich_00", "02_brm_rich_11", "03_brm_rich_12",
                    "04_brm_rich_12b", "05_brm_rich_20")
)) %>%
mutate(crop.pool = tolower(crop.pool))

rm(brm_rich_00_epred_trap.days, brm_rich_11_epred_trap.days,
   brm_rich_12_epred_trap.days, brm_rich_12b_epred_trap.days,
   brm_rich_20_epred_trap.days)

gc()

```

```

##          used (Mb) gc trigger (Mb) max used (Mb)
## Ncells  3371473 180.1 11471381 612.7 11471381 612.7
## Vcells 1156280047 8821.8 2107249941 16077.1 2107241324 16077.0

```

Pool activity density models

```

epred_activity_density <- bind_rows(brm_abund_00_epred,
                                    brm_abund_11_epred,
                                    brm_abund_12_epred,
                                    brm_abund_12b_epred,
                                    brm_abund_20_epred,
                                    brm_abund_30_epred,
                                    brm_abund_40_epred,
                                    brm_abund_50_epred) %>%
mutate(model = factor(
  model, levels = c("06_brm_abund_00", "07_brm_abund_11", "08_brm_abund_12",
                    "09_brm_abund_12b", "10_brm_abund_20", "11_brm_abund_30",
                    "12_brm_abund_40", "13_brm_abund_50")
)) %>%
mutate(crop.pool = tolower(crop.pool))

rm(brm_abund_00_epred, brm_abund_11_epred, brm_abund_12_epred,
   brm_abund_12b_epred, brm_abund_20_epred, brm_abund_30_epred,
   brm_abund_40_epred, brm_abund_50_epred)

gc()

```

```

##          used (Mb) gc trigger (Mb) max used (Mb)
## Ncells  3364307 179.7 9177105 490.2 11471381 612.7
## Vcells 1129504629 8617.5 2528779929 19293.1 2107241324 16077.0

```

Extract distance ranges to constrain plots

The max distances are the same across meta_rich and meta_abund, so I will just extract once from meta_rich

```
max_dist_crop <- meta_rich %>%
  group_by(crop.pool) %>%
  summarize(max.dist = max(distance100*100)) %>%
  mutate(crop.pool = tolower(crop.pool))

max_dist_snh <- meta_rich %>%
  group_by(snh.type) %>%
  summarize(max.dist = max(distance100*100))
```

Get average marginal and conditional effects

We average over SNH by grouping by distance, crop, and .draw, and taking the mean. This achieves the proper estimate because it makes it as though the study were balanced across crop and SNH. It removes the weighting effects of unequal sampling across crop and snh levels, because this is a synthetic data set where each is represented equally.

```
# By crop, averaged over habitat
epred_rich.crop <- epred_rich %>%
  group_by(model, distance, crop.pool, .draw) %>%
  summarize(.epred = mean(.epred)) %>%
  left_join(max_dist_crop)

epred_rich.trapdays.crop <- epred_rich.trapdays %>%
  group_by(model, log.trap.days, crop.pool, .draw) %>%
  summarize(.epred = mean(.epred)) %>%
  mutate(trap.days = exp(log.trap.days))

epred_activity_density.crop <- epred_activity_density %>%
  group_by(model, distance, crop.pool, .draw) %>%
  summarize(.epred = mean(.epred)) %>%
  left_join(max_dist_crop)

# By habitat, averaged over crop
epred_rich.snh <- epred_rich %>%
  group_by(model, distance, snh.type, .draw) %>%
  summarize(.epred = mean(.epred)) %>%
  left_join(max_dist_snh)

epred_rich.trapdays.snh <- epred_rich.trapdays %>%
  group_by(model, log.trap.days, snh.type, .draw) %>%
  summarize(.epred = mean(.epred)) %>%
  mutate(trap.days = exp(log.trap.days))

epred_activity_density.snh <- epred_activity_density %>%
  group_by(model, distance, snh.type, .draw) %>%
  summarize(.epred = mean(.epred)) %>%
  left_join(max_dist_snh)

# Finally, we can calculate a grand means by averaging over both crop and snh.type
epred_rich.grand <- epred_rich %>%
  group_by(model, distance, .draw) %>%
  summarize(.epred = mean(.epred))

epred_activity_density.grand <- epred_activity_density %>%
  group_by(model, distance, .draw) %>%
  summarize(.epred = mean(.epred))

#
# epred_pool3 <- bind_rows(brm_rich_00_epred,
#                          brm_rich_11_epred,
#                          brm_rich_12_epred,
```

```

#           brm_rich_12b_epred,
#           brm_rich_20_epred,
#           brm_abund_00_epred,
#           brm_abund_11_epred,
#           brm_abund_12_epred,
#           brm_abund_12b_epred,
#           brm_abund_20_epred,
#           brm_abund_30_epred,
#           brm_abund_40_epred,
#           brm_abund_50_epred) %>%
# mutate(model = factor(model, levels = c("01_brm_rich_00", "02_brm_rich_11",
#           "03_brm_rich_12", "04_brm_rich_12b",
#           "05_brm_rich_20", "06_brm_abund_00",
#           "07_brm_abund_11", "08_brm_abund_12",
#           "09_brm_abund_12b", "10_brm_abund_20",
#           "11_brm_abund_30", "12_brm_abund_40",
#           "13_brm_abund_50"))) %>%
# mutate(crop.pool = tolower(crop.pool))
#
#
#
# epred.grand3 <- epred_pool3 %>%
#   group_by(model, distance, .draw) %>%
#   summarize(.epred = mean(.epred))

# Revision
#
# epred.crop.revision <- epred_pool.revision %>%
#   group_by(model, distance, crop.pool, .draw) %>%
#   summarize(.epred = mean(.epred)) %>%
#   left_join(max_dist_crop)
#
# epred.snh.revision <- epred_pool.revision %>%
#   group_by(model, distance, snh.type, .draw) %>%
#   summarize(.epred = mean(.epred)) %>%
#   left_join(max_dist_snh)
#
# epred.grand.revision <- epred_pool.revision %>%
#   group_by(model, distance, .draw) %>%
#   summarize(.epred = mean(.epred))

```

Set up rugs for plotting

```

rich_rug00 <- get_rug(meta_rich, "01_brm_rich_00")
rich_rug11 <- get_rug(meta_rich, "02_brm_rich_11")
rich_rug12 <- get_rug(meta_rich, "03_brm_rich_12")
rich_rug12b <- get_rug(meta_rich, "04_brm_rich_12b")
rich_rug20 <- get_rug(meta_rich, "05_brm_rich_20")
activity_rug00 <- get_rug(meta_abund, "06_brm_abund_00")
activity_rug11 <- get_rug(meta_abund, "07_brm_abund_11")
activity_rug12 <- get_rug(meta_abund, "08_brm_abund_12")
activity_rug12b <- get_rug(meta_abund, "09_brm_abund_12b")
activity_rug20 <- get_rug(meta_abund, "10_brm_abund_20")
activity_rug30 <- get_rug(meta_abund, "11_brm_abund_30")

```

```

activity_rug40 <- get_rug(meta_abund, "12_brm_abund_40")
activity_rug50 <- get_rug(meta_abund, "13_brm_abund_50")

trap.days_rug <- meta_rich %>%
  select(log.trap.days) %>%
  mutate(trap.days = exp(log.trap.days)) %>%
  distinct()

rich_rug <- bind_rows(rich_rug00, rich_rug11, rich_rug12, rich_rug12b,
  rich_rug20) %>%
  mutate(model = factor(model, levels = c("01_brm_rich_00", "02_brm_rich_11",
    "03_brm_rich_12", "04_brm_rich_12b",
    "05_brm_rich_20"))) %>%
  mutate(crop.pool = tolower(crop.pool), distance = distance100 * 100)

activity_rug <- bind_rows(activity_rug00, activity_rug11, activity_rug12,
  activity_rug12b, activity_rug20, activity_rug30,
  activity_rug40, activity_rug50) %>%
  mutate(model = factor(model, levels = c("06_brm_abund_00", "07_brm_abund_11",
    "08_brm_abund_12", "09_brm_abund_12b",
    "10_brm_abund_20", "11_brm_abund_30",
    "12_brm_abund_40", "13_brm_abund_50"))) %>%
  mutate(crop.pool = tolower(crop.pool), distance = distance100 * 100)

```

Visualize

By crop

```

# Richness
ggplot(filter(epred_rich.crop, distance <= max.dist),
  aes(distance, .epred, fill = model)) +
  stat_lineribbon(aes(fill_ramp = stat(level))) +
  geom_rug(data = rich_rug, aes(distance), inherit.aes = FALSE) +
  labs(x = "distance [m]", y = "richness", fill = "Model", fill_ramp = "CI") +
  facet_grid(model ~ crop.pool,
    scales = "free_y") +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(strip.text.y = element_blank(),
    strip.background.y = element_blank(),
    panel.grid = element_blank(),
    legend.position="right") +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(order = 1),
    fill_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  scale_fill_discrete(labels = c("agg.",
    "pred.",
    "omniv.",
    "omniv. (-P. cup)",
    "graniv.)) +
  ggtitle("Richness ~ distance * crop")

```



```
# Richness * trapdays
ggplot(epred_rich.trapdays.crop,
  aes(trap.days, .epred, fill = model)) +
  stat_lineribbon(aes(fill_ramp = stat(level))) +
  geom_rug(data = trap.days_rug, aes(trap.days), inherit.aes = FALSE) +
  labs(x = "trap.days", y = "richness", fill = "Model", fill_ramp = "CI") +
  facet_grid(model ~ crop.pool,
    scales = "free_y") +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(strip.text.y = element_blank(),
    strip.background.y = element_blank(),
    panel.grid = element_blank(),
    legend.position="right") +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(order = 1),
    fill_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  scale_fill_discrete(labels = c("agg.",
    "pred.",
    "omniv.",
    "omniv. (-P. cup)",
    "graniv.)) +
  ggtitle("Richness ~ trapdays * crop")
```



```

# Activity density
ggplot(filter(epred_activity_density.crop, distance <= max.dist),
  aes(distance, .epred, fill = model)) +
  stat_lineribbon(aes(fill_ramp = stat(level))) +
  geom_rug(data = activity_rug, aes(distance), inherit.aes = FALSE) +
  labs(x = "distance [m]", y = "density", fill = "Model", fill_ramp = "CI") +
  facet_grid(model ~ crop.pool,
    scales = "free_y") +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(strip.text.y = element_blank(),
    strip.background.y = element_blank(),
    panel.grid = element_blank(),
    legend.position="right") +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(order = 1),
    fill_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  scale_fill_discrete(labels = c("agg.",
    "pred.",
    "omniv.",
    "omniv. (-P. cup)",
    "graniv.",
    "small",
    "medium",
    "large")) +
  ggtitle("Activity density ~ distance *crop")

```


By habitat

```

# Richness
ggplot(filter(epred_rich.snh, distance <= max.dist),
  aes(distance, .epred, fill = model)) +
  stat_lineribbon(aes(fill_ramp = stat(level))) +
  geom_rug(data = rich_rug, aes(distance), inherit.aes = FALSE) +
  labs(x = "distance [m]", y = "richness", fill = "Model", fill_ramp = "CI") +
  facet_grid(model ~ snh.type,
    scales = "free_y") +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(strip.text.y = element_blank(),
    strip.background.y = element_blank(),
    panel.grid = element_blank(),
    legend.position="right") +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(order = 1),
    fill_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  scale_fill_discrete(labels = c("agg.",
    "pred.",
    "omniv.",
    "omniv. (-P. cup)",
    "graniv.")) +
  ggtitle("Richness ~ distance * habitat")

```

Richness ~ distance * habitat


```
# Richness * trapdays
ggplot(epred_rich.trapdays.snh,
  aes(trap.days, .epred, fill = model)) +
  stat_lineribbon(aes(fill_ramp = stat(level))) +
  geom_rug(data = trap.days_rug, aes(trap.days), inherit.aes = FALSE) +
  labs(x = "trap.days", y = "richness", fill = "Model", fill_ramp = "CI") +
  facet_grid(model ~ snh.type,
    scales = "free_y") +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(strip.text.y = element_blank(),
    strip.background.y = element_blank(),
    panel.grid = element_blank(),
    legend.position="right") +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(order = 1),
    fill_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  scale_fill_discrete(labels = c("agg.",
    "pred.",
    "omniv.",
    "omniv. (-P. cup)",
    "graniv.)) +
  ggtitle("Richness ~ trapdays * habitat")
```

Richness ~ trapdays * habitat


```
# Activity density
ggplot(filter(epred_activity_density.snh, distance <= max.dist),
  aes(distance, .epred, fill = model)) +
  stat_lineribbon(aes(fill_ramp = stat(level))) +
  geom_rug(data = activity_rug, aes(distance), inherit.aes = FALSE) +
  labs(x = "distance [m]", y = "density", fill = "Model", fill_ramp = "CI") +
  facet_grid(model ~ snh.type,
    scales = "free_y") +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(strip.text.y = element_blank(),
    strip.background.y = element_blank(),
    panel.grid = element_blank(),
    legend.position="right") +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(order = 1),
    fill_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  scale_fill_discrete(labels = c("agg.",
    "pred.",
    "omniv.",
    "omniv. (-P. cup)",
    "graniv.",
    "small",
    "medium",
    "large")) +
  ggtitle("Activity density ~ distance *habitat")
```

Activity density ~ distance * habitat

Grand mean

```
# Richness
ggplot(epred_rich.grand, aes(distance, .epred, fill = model)) +
  stat_lineribbon(aes(fill_ramp = stat(level))) +
  geom_rug(data = rich_rug, aes(distance), inherit.aes = FALSE) +
  labs(x = "distance [m]", y = "richness", fill = "Model", fill_ramp = "CI") +
  facet_wrap(~model, scales = "free_y") +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(strip.text.y = element_blank(),
        strip.background.y = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        legend.position="right") +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(order = 1),
        fill_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  scale_fill_discrete(labels = c("agg.",
                                "pred.",
                                "omniv.",
                                "omniv. (-P. cup)",
                                "graniv.")) +
  ggtitle("Richness ~ distance")
```

Richness ~ distance


```
# Activity density
ggplot(epred_activity_density.grand, aes(distance, .epred, fill = model)) +
  stat_lineribbon(aes(fill_ramp = stat(level))) +
  geom_rug(data = activity_rug, aes(distance), inherit.aes = FALSE) +
  labs(x = "distance [m]", y = "density", fill = "Model", fill_ramp = "CI") +
  facet_wrap(~model, scales = "free_y") +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(strip.text.y = element_blank(),
        strip.background.y = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        legend.position="right") +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(order = 1),
         fill_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  scale_fill_discrete(labels = c("agg.",
                                "pred.",
                                "omniv.",
                                "omniv. (-P. cup)",
                                "graniv.",
                                "small",
                                "medium",
                                "large")) +
  ggtitle("Activity density ~ distance")
```

Activity density ~ distance

References

- Bürkner, Paul-Christian. 2017. “brms: An R Package for Bayesian Multilevel Models Using Stan.” *Journal of Statistical Software* 80 (1): 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v080.i01>.
- Kay, Matthew. 2020. *tidybayes: Tidy Data and Geoms for Bayesian Models*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1308151>.